

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel(II) with 2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime

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In continuation of our earlier work on the use of 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime (2-HANO) as an organic analytical reagent in the estimation of metals¹, we report here the spectrophotometric study of nickel(II) with the reagent. The yellow nickel(II) complex formed in the pH range 7.0–12.0 and quantitatively extractable in chloroform, absorbs at 385 nm.

Results and Discussion

At pH 9.0 the chloroform extract of Ni^{II}-2HANO complex showed maximum absorbance. Besides chloroform, other organic solvents viz. carbon tetrachloride, n-butanol and benzene were examined as extractants, and chloroform proved to be the best solvent. At least 10–15 fold excess of the reagent was necessary for maximum colour development.

The system obeyed Beer's law in the range 4.0–45.0 ppm of Ni^{II} in 10 ml of chloroform at 385 nm. Studies made using Job's method², mole-ratio method³, slope-ratio method⁴ and Asmus method⁵ indicated that 2-HANO formed a 1:2 (metal-ligand) complex with Ni^{II}. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and stability constant (Asmus method) at 30° of the complex were found to be $7.98 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.0073 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 1.72×10^8 respectively.

Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ba^{II}, Hg^{II}, Ca^{II} and Cr^{III} upto 50 ppm and Ti^{IV} and UO₂^{II} upto 20 ppm did not interfere. Chloride, carbonate, sulphite, sulphate, acetate, bromide and iodide did not interfere even when present in 10-fold excess of Ni^{II}. Interference due to cobalt could be prevented by extracting it into isoamyl alcohol in presence of thiocyanate prior to the addition of 2-HANO. Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} could be masked with phosphate.

The nickel content in a nichrome wire sample was determined by the present method and the

results were compared with that obtained by atomic absorption spectrometry. Four such determinations indicated constant results: average Ni found (%) 59.03 and 59.39 by 2-HANO and AAS methods respectively.

Experimental

The reagent was prepared⁶, recrystallised with rectified spirit and dried in vacuum under reduced pressure. A stock solution of nickel(II) was prepared by dissolving ammonium nickel chloride (AnalaR) in double-distilled water and standardised⁷. Ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer was used to adjust the pH. Distilled chloroform was used as extractant. An Elico 10 pH meter and a Shimadzu-UV 240 spectrophotometer were used.

An aliquot containing $\leq 25 \mu\text{g}$ of Ni^{II} was treated with 0.025% 2-HANO (3.0 ml) and the pH was adjusted to 9.0 by adding required amount of the buffer. The mixture was left for 2 min and then shaken vigorously with chloroform (10 ml) for 2 min. The organic phase was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance of the chloroform extract was measured at 385 nm against the reagent blank.

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